

A Quantum Mechanical Approach to the Theory of Cancer from Polynuclear Molecules. Metabolic Activation and Carcinogenicity of Methylphenanthrenes

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Metabolism and cancer-inducing ability of methylphenanthrenes are determined using quantum mechanical method in the MINDO/3 approximations of Bingham *et al.* Several reactivity and molecular parameters are used for the purpose. Results of the calculations indicate that none of the isomeric methylphenanthrenes are active as cancer initiator and that 1,2-diol-3,4-epoxide which is the ultimate metabolite for each of them is very weak. The predictions are in striking agreement with the experiment.

THE rapid increase in the number of known chemical carcinogens^{1, 2} from one (dibenz(a,h)anthracene) in 1929 to several hundreds at the present time has opened up unparallel scope of developments in the study of chemical carcinogens. Recently it has become apparent that many chemical carcinogens including PAHs require metabolic activation^{3, 4} in order to be able to react with cellular macromolecules and exert their biological effects. There are a number of techniques for the study of metabolic activations and various strains on which these methods can be applied. So far, works have been carried out in whole animals⁵, in cells in culture^{6, 7}, in tissues in short term organ cultures⁸, and in tissue preparations derived from a variety of sources⁹. There are differences in the products obtained from various types of experiments. However, the overall pattern of metabolites in all the cases is the same. When a PAH is metabolized a number of isomeric dihydrodiols are theoretically formed on the peripheral double bonds throughout the molecule. These dihydrodiols are next metabolized to diol-epoxides either by metabolism at adjacent olefinic double bonds or at aromatic bonds in other rings of the molecule. In the case of methylated hydrocarbons, the hydroxylation of methyl group(s) may also occur, which increases the possible number of dihydrodiols/diol-epoxides.

The substitution of methyl group for hydrogen at various positions of the aromatic ring structures of PAHs changes their carcinogenic activities^{5, 10, 11}. These changes seem to stem from steric interactions in which the methyl group alters the electronic distributions of the molecule. Methyl group is electron donor and is able to provide additional charge for the aromatic backbone of the methylated PAH. Incidentally, there is an alternative possibility in which no charge is migrated from the methyl group but an enhanced conjugation takes place. A situation

can also arise in which one can think of superposition of both the possibilities. Whatever be the mechanism, the net effect is that the methylation modifies the metabolic processes, and yields either a highly reactive dihydrodiol (diol-epoxide), or deactivates the compound.

In recent years a number of workers have carried out investigations on the carcinogenic activities of methylated PAHs. The compounds include BP, BA, chrysene, phenanthrene and fluoranthene^{5, 10-13}. Using a two stage procedure to initiate skin tumors in mice Iyer *et al.*¹⁰ have found that 11-MBP is about three times as active as the parent compound. In the case of BA 7-MBA exhibits much higher carcinogenicity than the BA itself⁵. Chrysene is almost inactive, but 5-methylchrysene is highly carcinogenic¹³. Recent observations¹⁴ indicate that this compound, when tested on animals, shows carcinogenicity equivalent to that of BP. Phenanthrene is perhaps the only compound in which methylation does not induce any change of carcinogenicity. LaVoie *et al.*^{11, 15} have determined the mutagenicity, *in vitro* metabolism, and tumor initiating ability of MePs. Similar to the parent compound (Fig. 1) none of the methyl derivatives was found active on the mouse skin.

We are in the process of developing the theory of carcinogenicity of polycyclic hydrocarbons using

Fig. 1. Molecular structure of phenanthrene.

Abbreviations: PAH, polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbon; BP, benzo(a)pyrene; BA, benzo(a)anthracene; MBA, methylbenzo(a)anthracene; MBP, methylbenzo(a)pyrene; MeP, methylphenanthrenes.

self-consistent-field (SCF) molecular orbital (MO) method. The theory is applied to alternant hydrocarbons^{15,16}, non-alternant hydrocarbons (fluoranthrene)¹⁷, MBAs¹⁸, MBPs¹⁹, and methylchrysenes²⁰ with striking success. The purpose of the present paper is to examine the applicability of the theory to MePs.

Outline of theoretical method :

There are diversity in the characteristics of PAHs. In view of this and that there are many factors involved in the modifications of biological activities, no single chemical or physical properties can be fully correlated with the carcinogenicity of the compounds. Our theory makes use of a number of molecular properties and reactivity indices in an effort to elucidate various aspects of carcinogenic characteristics of the compounds.

The theory is based on the all-valence electron-SCF-MO method with MINDO/3 approximations of Bingham *et al.*²¹. Due to molecular symmetry there are only five unique monomethyl derivatives of phenanthrene. The relatively narrow range of activity exhibited by these derivatives requires that these materials be tested under identical conditions in order to produce meaningful results for comparison. It is obviously very difficult to achieve the exact identical conditions. In order to keep scope for considerations in case any inconsistency results from the non-satisfaction of ideal conditions we carried out calculations for all the MePs. In the MO methods the results are highly sensitive to the choice of geometry of the test molecules. Using a stepwise optimization procedure we optimized the geometry of phenanthrene in an earlier paper¹⁵ of the series. In the present investigation this geometry is adopted as the fixed skeleton backbone, except that the methyl groups substituted for the hydrogen atoms are individually optimized. Fletcher-Powell-Davidon minimization technique^{22,23} is applied for optimization.

Results and Discussion

In earlier investigations¹⁵⁻²⁰ we considered $R_{AB}(\pi)$, $R_L(\pi)$, $R_f(\pi)$ and E_{AB} as possible indices for the metabolic activation of PAHs. $R_{AB}(\pi)$ and E_{AB} , among them, came out as the most effective indices. In the present investigation we confine ourselves only to these indices. The values V_{1k} of $R_{AB}(\pi)$ and V_{2k} of E_{AB} corresponding to various peripheral/terminal bonds k ($k=1, 2, 3, 4$. .) of MePs are listed in Table 1. Results for the bridgehead unreactive carbon atoms and bonds are not however presented in the Table. The calculations have been carried out in the double precision to ensure that the presented data are accurate at least up to four decimal places. According to our earlier classifications MePs having bay-regions are group I molecules in which the ultimate metabolite should be a bay-region diol-epoxide. If we rearrange V_{1k} ($j=1, 2$) in the decreasing order, *viz.* to $V_{11} > V_{12} > V_{13}$. .) the bond X_{11} corresponding to V_{11} would represent the site of dihydrodiol; that (*e.g.* X_{21}) corresponding to V_{21} to the site of epoxide. The bond

TABLE 1—CALCULATED BOND REACTIVITY INDICES^a OF METHYLPHENANTHRENES

Location of methyl group	Bond (A - B)				
	1-2	3-4	5-6	7-8	9-10
1	0.1144 20.879	0.1144 20.867	0.1168 21.887	0.1160 21.869	0.1178 21.576
2	0.1145 20.862	0.1146 20.852	0.1170 21.876	0.1161 21.527	0.1182 21.579
3	0.1143 20.879	0.1143 20.867	0.1161 21.869	0.1167 21.922	0.1178 21.586
4	0.1140 20.875	0.1141 20.700	0.1159 21.018	0.1170 21.895	0.1174 21.590
5	0.1142 20.869	0.1142 20.863	0.1169 21.914	0.1169 21.940	0.1170 21.937

^a Upper and lower results in each row correspond to $-R_{AB}(\pi)$ and $-E_{AB}$ (eV), respectively.

X_{12} with energy V_{12} which belongs to bay-region would represent the site of epoxidation. In the case of E_{AB} the bond X_{22} belongs to region distal to the bay and represents the site of dihydrodiol. From Table 1 it is apparent that the values of $R_{AB}(\pi)$ for all of the MePs are extremely insensitive to the choice of bond. This implies that no effective metabolite results from the biological activation of the molecules, or conversely, the metabolites are formed, but are very weak, and are unable to initiate cancer. The implication is consistent with our observations in the earlier investigation¹⁵ which is completely in agreement with the experiments. The distribution of predicted metabolites is summarized in Table 2. For all MePs the predicted ultimate metabolite is 1,2-diol-3,4-epoxide with epoxide formed in the bay-region and the diol in region distal to it. The 9,10-bonds of MePs correspond to the K-regions. The predicted metabolite of this bond, according to our postulates, is an oxide (or dihydrodiol). One fundamental hypothesis of the K-region theory of Pullman and Pullman²⁴ is that the interaction between the carcinogen and cellular receiver takes place through the K-region of the carcinogen. The interaction is of electrostatic nature and is effective when an oxide is formed in the K-region. Contrary to the assumptions of Pullman and Pullman, results in Table 2 indicate that the K-region oxides are the least reactive and can not be related to cancer.

As an attempt to explain the carcinogenic strengths various molecular properties of MePs are listed in Table 3. Almost identical results for 1- and 8-, 2- and 7-, 3- and 6-, and 4- MePs which are equivalent indicate that the geometry is constructed quite consistently. Table 3 includes energies of the highest occupied MO (HOMO) (say, the n th.MO), E_{H1} , and of the lowest unoccupied MO (LUMO) ($(n+1)$ th.MO), E_{L1} . The excitation potential, E_p is a measure of energy required by an electron to jump from the HOMO to the LUMO. It may be related to the ease of carbonium ion formation in a compound. E_p values for various MePs are also included in Table 3. The values of E_{H1} and E_p suggest that 4-MeP is the most reactive among all methyl derivatives of phenanthrene. It is followed by 1-,

TABLE 2—SUMMARY OF PREDICTED METABOLITES OF METHYLPHENANTHRENES

Molecule	Most probable metabolite (ultimate metabolite)	2nd. probable metabolite	3rd. probable metabolite
1 MeP	1,2-Diol-3,4-epoxide	7,8-Diol-5,6-epoxide	9,10-Oxide
2-MeP	1,2-Diol-3,4-epoxide	5,6-Diol-7,8-epoxide	7,8-Diol-5,6-epoxide
3-MeP	1,2-Diol-3,4-epoxide	7,8-Diol-5,6-epoxide	9,10-Oxide
4-MeP	1,2-Diol-3,4-epoxide	5,6-Diol-7,8-epoxide	7,8-Diol-5,6-epoxide
9 MeP	1,2-Diol-3,4-epoxide 3,4-Diol-1,2-epoxide	5,6-Diol-7,8-epoxide	9,10-Oxide

 TABLE 3—CHARACTERISTIC MOLECULAR PROPERTIES^a
OF METHYLPHENANTHRENES

Location of methyl group	D _{CM}	-E _{CM}	-E _{H1}	E _{L1}	E _P
1	1.508	15.365	7.882	0.181	8.013
2	1.506	15.367	7.909	0.204	8.104
3	1.504	15.404	7.854	0.184	3.088
4	1.524	14.491	7.799	0.232	8.031
5	1.513	15.079	7.773	0.200	7.973
6	1.504	15.431	7.843	0.186	8.029
7	1.503	15.425	7.865	0.237	8.102
8	1.504	15.474	7.862	0.212	8.074
9	1.508	15.357	7.831	0.186	8.017
10	1.509	15.379	7.821	0.165	7.986

^aExcept for D_{CM} which is in Å all other molecular quantities are in eV.

and 9-MePs. The prediction by E_{L1} is little different, according to which 2-, and 9-MePs followed by 4-MeP are the most reactive. E_{H1} is, in fact, equivalent to the first ionization potential, and E_{L1} to the electron affinity of MePs. The lower the ionization potential, the greater is the chance of carbonium ion formation in a compound. Similarly, the higher the electron affinity, the more electrophilic is the compound, and greater is the probability of interaction between carcinogen and DNA. Due to steric hindrance from a methyl group at position 4 the metabolite which is formed in the region is likely to get detoxified. In phenanthrene (Fig. 1) 1, 2, 3, and 4 positions which are equivalent to 8, 7, 6 and 5 positions, respectively also form part of the same bay. 4-Methyl group is at peri position with respect to the second bay-region terminal ring. It, therefore, appears that 4-MeP can be the most reactive in case the metabolite is formed in the second terminal ring. The first and second columns of Table 3 list the distance D_{CM}, between the methyl carbon and the backbone carbon directly attached to the methyl group, and the total two center electronic energy E_{CM}, between the same carbon atoms, respectively. High positive value of D_{CM} and least negative value of E_{CM} reaffirm that 4-MeP is the most carcinogenic in the series. Availability of quantitative data from high precision experiment justifies validity of the above predictions.

Conclusion :

The results reported in the present article lend strong supports to the idea that electronic para-

eters determined by quantum mechanical method are able to elucidate carcinogenic properties of MePs. To our knowledge, no experimental results are available to provide comparison with predicted metabolic products. Yang *et al.*²⁶ undertook studies of the metabolism of twelve MBAs, with rat liver microsomes. They observed that with the exception of 3-MBA, the proximate metabolite for all other eleven MBAs was 3,4-diol. The metabolite is identical to that of BA. In the case of phenanthrene the proximate metabolite is 1,2-diol. On the basis of observations for MBAs that contrary to usual generalization^{26,27}, microsomal enzymes may epoxidize the aromatic double bond with a methyl substituent, and the epoxides may be subsequently hydrated to dihydrodiols by the microsomal epoxide hydrase, the proximate metabolite of MePs should also be 1,2-diol. In case it is true, the predicted metabolites would be in quantitative agreement with the experiments.

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